

ISLAMIC ECONOMIC MODEL: FEATURES, CURRENT STATE AND PROSPECTS FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article discusses the key features of one of the national models of modern mixed economy, namely the Islamic economic model, and the impact of these features on the economic, legal and economic activities of the subjects of Islamic entrepreneurship. The basic principles on which to build the functioning of this system, and the tools by which they are observed. The author analyzes the correctness of the use of the concept of "Islamic economy" and justifies the correctness of this concept in conjunction with the "Islamic economic model» The relevance of this topic is due to the growing scientific interest in the study and further implementation of the Islamic economy in different regions of the world.

Keywords: Islam, Islamic economy, Islamic economic model, Sharia, zakat, riba, garar

Introduction. The modern world economic system in the conditions of the crisis turned out to be vulnerable and at the same time such that it affects the macroeconomic stability of national economies. Governments of almost all countries rushed to look for effective ways of macroeconomic stabilization of national economies, rapidly losing balance due to the impact through global financial channels. Under these conditions, the least affected countries were those that at that time, to varying degrees, applied elements of the Islamic economic concept in banking and financial activities. This is what causes research interest in the Islamic economic system, the system of Islamic economic relations, including financial, banking Islamic economics is a Sharia point of view, which includes a number of Islamic principles and economic indicators, as well as an analysis of how economic reforms are carried out in accordance with these principles and indicators.

In the Islamic world, the theoretical concept of Islamic economics is not only widely used, but also takes place in real official institutions (Islamic management, Islamic banks, Islamic insurance institutions, etc.). The emergence of Islamic economic thought is associated with the names of al-Ghazali (XI-XII centuries), Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn Qaim Jauzia (turn of XIII-XIV centuries), Ibn Khaldun (turn of XIV-XV centuries). These scientists were not called economists, so economics touched only theological aspects in their writings. In his theory, al-Ghazali considers all economic activity as an integral part of the fulfillment of religious duty. It is permissible to use the term "Islamic economic model" as a synonym for Islamic economics. A science that studies the principles and methods of business activity in accordance with Sharia law can also be called Islamic economic science. Some scholars mistakenly equate the Islamic and interest-free economy. The functioning of the Islamic economic model can be discussed in cases where Islamic methods of financing are used. The interest-free system, in turn, usually exists within the framework of the underdevelopment of the financial sector in traditional societies, and as the interest-free nature of the economy disappears. As an example of a country with an interest-free or, rather, quasi-interest-free financial system, Somaliland can be cited, an unrecognized state in the north of the Somali Peninsula, where there are no banks charging or paying loan interest [9]. It is no exaggeration to say that the interest-free financing model is more consistent with Sharia law than with some dubious "halal" products invented by banks and other financial institutions to attract Muslim customers. In the face of fierce competition with traditional banks and insurance companies, it is not always easy for Islamic financial institutions to find an average decade between the attractiveness of the relevant products for their customers and 100% compliance with Sharia. So far, Islamic banks and takaful companies have

followed the path of creating analogues of existing traditional banking and insurance products. A distinctive feature of the Islamic economic model as a set of production models, in contrast to the market economy, is that in the Islamic model, profit maximization is not in the first place, yielding to the selection method of obtaining this profit. There is one important point that separates it from the traditional economic system - a moral orientation based on the ethical limitations of religion. In this case, the main criterion is compatibility with Sharia. Firstly, the limitations of permitted business in the sphere of activity of Muslim entrepreneurs, for example, there is a ban on gambling, business for the production of tobacco, alcohol or narcotic products, as well as the use of property and income received from such activities. Thus, the valuation of property in Islam is directly dependent on religious conditions [2].

Secondly, based on the position of Islamic law, the economic activity and behavior of participants involved in market relations should comply with the principle of high integrity. This principle assumes that the participants necessarily fix the subject, conditions and obligations of the contract, as well as the prohibition of any coercion at the conclusion of the contract, the obligation to comply with its terms, readiness for good faith, free access to the market of trade participants, honesty in all trade relations, providing complete and reliable information about the quality, quantity of goods, prices and conditions of further trade. All the negative factors, such as fraud, speculation, monopoly, turn out to be all of the law [3]. The Islamic economic model, based on Islamic values and worldview, is only an integral part of the entire Islamic system, in which religious norms prevail rather, through which economic activity has been integrated into social life and standards of correct social behavior. These principles regulate and control the socio-economic life of a person, dominating the

economy, and not vice versa. The Islamic economic system not only explains socio-economic phenomena, but also regulates economic behavior. The Islamic economic model is based on the principle of functioning based on real assets, the rejection of usury and other prohibited instruments. The absence of these tools helps to avoid crisis phenomena. In the traditional system, there are many elements that contribute to inflating the financial bubble: derivatives add-ons allow you to make debts, one of the main elements of the modern Western economic model is the theory of interest. In Islam, any percentage is strictly prohibited. This prohibition allows the debt burden to be distributed equally, defining debt either as financial assistance on a returnable basis, or as an investment in the broadest sense of the word. We can talk about the principles of social justice in the implementation of various investment instruments. Many theorists of the Islamic economic model claim in their research that the economy cannot be truly effective if it is not based on the principles of social justice and responsibility. The peculiarity of the Islamic economic model is expressed not so much in some quantitative indicators, the level of income and expenses, import and export volumes and other economic statistics. It is largely due to moral and ethical imperatives, a ban on the occupation of certain "unrighteous" areas of business, a ban on the use of income from these areas, restrictions on the model of economic behavior. Sharia establishes the following basic principles that define the main features of the Islamic economic model. 1) Zakat is a kind of capital tax in favor of certain categories of needy Muslims; it is included in the list of the most important duties of a Muslim, the five pillars of Islam. The obligation to give Zakat is fixed in the Koran 2) Riba (translated from Arabic – "increment, surplus, usury") - a ban on loan interest, usury and any unjustified capital increment in the implementation of trade and financial transactions. In fact, the concept of "riba"

includes any predetermined rate that depends on the timing and size of the loan and does not depend on the success of the investment. As an example, the Qur'an points to the business behavior of Jews who practiced financial transactions based on *riba*, including in the Arabian Peninsula 3) *Garar* (translated from Arabic "danger") - a ban on the use of an element of uncertainty, randomness or ambiguity in the subject and conditions of the contract, including the price - in general, everything that may entail the risk of speculative earnings. The definition of "*garar*" includes "*maysir*" – all kinds of lotteries, casinos, gambling [1]. In order to comply with the above principles, the Islamic world has developed a set of operations, mechanisms and tools for carrying out economic activities. 1) *Bai'* (translated from Arabic - "sale") is a contract of sale under which the seller undertakes to transfer the goods and transfer ownership to the buyer.

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